

Journal for Current Sign

Online ISSN (3006-1504)

Print ISSN (3006-1490)

PERCEPTION OF TEACHERS ABOUT STUDENTS LEARNING OUTCOMES BASED EXAMINATION AT HIGHER SECONDARY SCHOOL LEVEL

Waseem Sadiq

Dr. Sufi Amin

Dr. Shaheen Ashraf Tahirkheli

<https://currentsignjournal.com/index.php/JCS/index>

HJRS HEC Journal Recognition System

Perception of Teachers About Students Learning Outcomes Based Examination at Higher Secondary School Level

Waseem Sadiq

Former Research Scholar, Department of Educational Leadership and Management, Faculty of Education, International Islamic University Islamabad

Dr. Sufi Amin

Assistant Professor, Department of Educational Leadership and Management, Faculty of Education, International Islamic University Islamabad

Email: sufi.amin@iiu.edu.pk

Dr. Shaheen Ashraf Tahirkheli

Former Research Scholar, Mohi-Ud-Din Islamic University, Nerian Sharif AJ&K

Abstract

Students' Learning outcomes policy has changed the prospects of viewing education in Pakistan. As the new curriculum introduced many rudimental changes in educational practices. One of them was the SLOs based examination system. SLO is defined as "being something that students can do now that they could not do previously, a change in people as a result of a learning experience" (Watson, 2002). SLOs based examination has been initiated recently by Federal Board Intermediate and Secondary Education. This change has tremendous potential to affect all stakeholders. The objectives of the study were to: find out the perceptions of SLOs based examination at HSSC Level. Descriptive survey with questionnaires was developed through a quantitative approach to evaluate the perception of teachers about SLOs based examination. The population of the study was composed of all the HSSC level teachers and students to inquire about the phenomenon under investigation. Data was analysed by using SPSS and the researcher analysed the data according to the objectives of the study. The perceptions of SLOs were apparent and were in favour of SLOs based examination. It is concluded that the panic among teachers, students and parents is how the process of setting goals, monitoring and evaluation was observed as these are the rudiments of learning. The biggest achievement SLOs based teaching learning process makes is that students start thinking, but when they are let to move toward unseen contents that could be tested in an examination, they get strayed and here lies the

problem. Now, may we curtail their thinking in a boundary by delimiting the content or may we continue the experiment of SLOs based examination.

Keywords: Students' Learning outcomes, Educational Practices, SLOs based examination, Secondary Level

Introduction

To change the impact of education, the innovating policies have been coined around the world, and the impacts are infinite. Students Learning Outcomes based learning is comparatively a new phenomenon in Pakistan. It was there but the ratio of each Bloom's taxonomy learning outcome (Adams, 2015) was different and focus was on knowledge-based questions. There were pros and cons of that system (Bashir, 2018). The major flaw of the previous system was rote learning and the cramming habit (Ahmed, 2017) that was the top most priority of all students. When the shift from knowledge-based questions to application-based questions in the annual system was introduced, it ultimately affected the formative testing in the internal examination system as well as the summative testing in the external examination system adopted by different boards and certificate awarding institutes (Choy, 2009). The effects were manifold and the stakeholders have been confused whether this change has an optimistic or pessimistic effects on the overall learning of the students (Nolberto, 2021) as some of them have neglected the retention and the level of keeping information intact in their brain resultantly tilted towards downfall (Yilmaz, 2022). This phenomenon could surely have a long-lasting effect on the overall learning process and the future generations of professionals could reflect it as SLOs based learning emphasises concepts and comprehension rather than knowledge retention. The way students are assessed affects their preparation for certain examinations (Senyamator, 2022). The students used to spend a lot of time memorising content for the final exam as it was tested in a way that the students who had memorised more would have achieved better grades.

Assessment is believed to be a touchstone in the educational system that plays an important role in impacting various processes like lesson planning, teaching, learning, application of learning and decision-making along with curriculum development, and policy making (Coombs et al. 2018). SLOs system is a complete, compact and inclusive procedure of

generating, formatting and registering academic growth and targets of learners in computable terms. (Iqbal, et al. 2019) All the aligned information and data i.e. students' registrations, teachers' records, learners' specific demographics belonging, the standard set for specific learning and assessment practices. SLOs focus on the student's learning aims, targets and compulsions (Balch, et al. 2015). SLO assists the educators with chances to make a specific plan to the standard and clear target of growth of the learners through the assessment process aligned to meet the standards of the classroom educational instructions. By processing so, precise, analogous and attainable growth targets are required to be fixed. (Anderson, 1988). Students Learning Outcomes (SLOs) based testing has been there to open doors of innovation and to instil the love for curiosity not only in the teachers but also in the students.

In the previous strategy the teacher had a plan to execute and his point of view was what he/ she has to achieve but the new strategy is totally opposite to the existing one and now the learning outcome is how the students need to be developed. It is as in the past how I see a thing but now how it looks. Surely, this approach is more pragmatic and result oriented. What I want to see in the student is different from how the student looks. Each student is important in Students Learning Outcomes (SLOs) based testing. As it is not a single size fits all. It was easy for a teacher to tell the learner to reproduce the material. But now comprehension is important and the students should reach to the optimum level and show the skill that was taught rather than just cramming, the students have to digest the information and produce the output as per required standard.

Statement of the Problem

Student Learning Outcomes based examination has been comparatively a new phenomenon in Pakistan. This created a panic among teachers, students and parents as it is how the process of setting goals, monitoring and evaluation has been done because these are the rudiments of SLOs base learning. It is quite apparent that SLOs are measurable instructional goals for a specific group of students for a period of time. It supports instructions and lets teachers know the boundaries of each topic.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives of the study were to find out teachers' perceptions of SLOs at English language learning at HSSC Level. Research question was: What are the Teachers' perceptions of SLOs based examination of English language at HSSC level?

Literature Review

Students Learning Outcomes are declaratives of the measurable knowledge, skills and abilities that an individual should achieve and who can do at the completion of a learning process or sequence of learning activities. It is essential that statements must be quantitative, specific not general, well defined, clear and concise terms that encompass the specific skills students should be able to understand, demonstrate, perform and produce at the end of a specific course in a curriculum.

Spady, one of the leading propagators of SLOs, said that the design, development, and documenting of educational instructions in which targets are specifically predefined. His belief is the curriculum need to be developed after an educational institution properly defines the outcomes that they wish for learners to be attained when graduating. Learning outcomes have multi-dimensional effects. They are not only isolated tools at the level of assessment rather it is reflected in curriculum design, methodology of pedagogy etc. SLOs also play a pivotal role in the correlation of academic and vocational education and training, furthermore the development of constant learning activities their qualifications frameworks and the development of credit hours transfer and calculation of grade systems. They provide the groundwork and the new ideas for the architecture of educational and learning reforms.

Schwarz and Cavener said that SLOs can be described as an educational method that concentrates not only on what students learn rather on what the method used for learning. It begins with the basic concept of that all learner can attain certain skills and be successful. SLO refers to a specific structural framework at a school that stresses clearly predefined learning outcomes, the ways of measurement of success, pedagogical steps planning instructions directly related to learner's abilities and needs, adjustable usage of time period and learning opportunities,

Journal for Current Sign

Online ISSN (3006-1504)

Print ISSN (3006-1490)

approves and appreciate student success, and modify the programs on the basis of learners' results analysis (Biondin-Andrew, 1998).

Origin of Students Learning Outcomes

Students Learning outcomes origin cannot be traced quite accurately (Adam, 2006). The initiation of SLOs can be approximately traced back in history to the late 19th and early 20th centuries. The work of a famous educationist, Ivan Pavlov, who describes an unconditioned stimulus is something that naturally and automatically triggers a response without any learning. JB Watson and BF Skinner in America, famous psychologists, contributed a lot for basic learning process. Pavlov did very famous experiments that was associated with the conditioning of specific dogs and automatic learning style. Other psychologists, Watson and Skinner, pioneered the behaviourist approach that explains human behaviour regarding responses to external stimuli (Ryan, et al. 2019). This approach paved the way for SLOs method.

Without considering Skinner's strange ideas on mass conditioning, programmed and planned instruction and the excesses of his intense views, his work led to productive research that developed American education process, i.e. teaching, learning and training methods in business, industry and the armed forces. (Bakia, et al. 2012) Behaviourism stressed while elaborating the clear identification and measurement of learning and the need to produce observable and measurable learning outcomes (Chaplain, 2008). This philosophy, behaviourism, provided the basis of SLOs. As a result, the Students Learning Outcomes based approach was refined by educationist in countries i.e. Australia, (Berlach, 2004) New Zealand, South Africa and the UK. Most recently Denmark, Sweden, Ireland and other parts of Europe also opted the change. With this perilous start, the focus on learning outcomes has gradually developed to encompass all subject areas engulfing whole curricula, and has moved from school and vocational education and training (VET) fields through to higher education. The major advantage is the clarity and precision that was brought to the curriculum development process.

Prevalence of Students Learning Outcome

It is a relatively new phenomenon in Pakistan as FBlSE Islamabad initiated this in 2019, but it has been prevalent in many countries around the world. Currently in South Africa, and other countries of the world such as the

United Kingdom, the United States, Canada, Australia and New Zealand SLOs based education has been implemented. (Mkhatshwa, 1997). Literature review elaborates a mixture of both positive and negative attitudes towards students learning outcome-based education. The articles such as "Outcomes-Based Education: Miracle Cure or Plague" (Manno, 1994) and "What is OBE: A White Knight to the Rescue or a Disaster in the Making?" (Bonville, 1996) point out the conflicting nature of SLOs based education.

Teaching Objectives vs. Students Learning Outcomes

Teaching Objectives	Student Learning Outcomes
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▶ Based on the teacher's perception of what children should know ▶ Secondly, help teachers plan their teaching strategies ▶ Teachers give their opinion of student's performance to parents ▶ In addition, students are compared with each other 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developed by professionals, they are based on children-specific learning needs Guide teachers select the best learning activities for students Evaluate student's performance on the basis of expected outcomes Each student was evaluated individually

Challenges of SLOs-Based Examination

The real challenges of SLOs-Based examination are developing SLOs, aligning instruction with the SLOs and developing effective assessments instruction. It depends on the expertise of teachers who have been teaching the courses that how they can face these challenges the more effective they are the more it is easier for them to meet the challenges. The impact depends on setting the targets properly and leading students through those paths that acquaint them with the future challenges.

Developing SLOs

Developing SLOs that are Specific, measurable, and achievable, reliable and time bound can be challenging (Conzemius, et al. 2009). It is really important to involve faculty, students, staff and other stakeholders in the SLO development process to ensure that the SLOs are relevant, specific and result-oriented. While developing SLOs the stakeholders needs to have the following in their minds: clarity and precision, alignment with curriculum,

measurability and assessment, numbers of objects neither too much nor too few, stakeholder's effective involvement, resistance to change, sustainability, cultural and linguistic diversity, integration of technology, and data analysis and utilization. To achieve the proper development, collaborative and proactive approach along with enriching involvement of faculty, section heads, principals, administrators and stakeholders is required, moreover students' participation cannot be ignored at any time. Their feed should be taken from time to time and especially after the completion of the course (Meng, 2020). In addition to it, alumni should also be contacted to find out the real-world challenges.

Aligning instruction with the SLOs

The ever-changing process of education along with ever changing SLOs, it is difficult to cope up with the issue of aligning instructions with the SLOs. The objectives need to be very clear while keeping such ideas in mind that the understanding of the students' interest and style of learning is essential (Biggs, 1999). The selection of activities and implementation of certain practical work needs to be considered. Constant students' learning evaluation is also really very important. Selecting appropriate instructional activities. There are a variety of instructional activities that can be used to help students achieve SLOs (Yelamarthi, et al. 2014). However, it can be difficult to select the activities that are most appropriate for a particular course or program. Implementing the instructional activities effectively. Once instructional activities have been selected, faculty need to implement them effectively. This includes providing students with clear instructions, providing opportunities for students to practise the skills and knowledge that they are learning, and providing feedback to students on their progress (Sadler, 2014).

Research Methodology

Descriptive survey type design was used. In view of the related literature review, questionnaires were developed through a quantitative approach to evaluate the problems and issues of SLOs based examination for HSSC students of Taxila. The survey research provided numeral description of tendencies, trends, attitudes, and opinions of a population. By studying and investigating a sample of that population which included cross-sectional

and longitudinal studies using specially designed questionnaires for data gathering, (Babbie, 1990) while generalizing the sample to the population. The selection population of this study consisted of all the high secondary level teachers and students in government and private colleges of Tehsil Taxila to inquire about the phenomenon under investigation. There were 27 higher secondary schools having 5210 students and 110 ESL teachers in Tehsil Taxila that are affiliated with FBlSE.

The selected sample of this study comprised of 357 students with systematic random sampling where every fifth student in the list was selected and all ESL 110 teachers from the HSSC level institutes. The sample size of this study was determined by applying criteria given by Johnson & Christensen (2000). As per the criteria provided, if the size of population contains (N=5000) then the recommended size of sample could be n= 317 to adequately represent the population. The Questionnaires were used to gather data from students to find out the problems and issues of the SLOs based examination system of English language writing skills. The researcher visited the colleges and gathered primary data from the students and the teachers' data.

Questionnaires were used for research procedures as they provide a comparative quick, efficient and economical means of collecting large amounts of data from selected sample of population. This tool is particularly effective for measuring subject behaviour, trends, intentions, tendencies and opinions of the selected population. Questionnaires' usage of open and closed research questions enables researchers to get both qualitative and quantitative data, resulting in more comprehensive results. Questionnaires provide practicality, efficiency, speed, comparability, scalability, standardisation, comfort of participant, and easy analysis of the collected data.

Table 1: Table of Five Point Likert Scale Questionnaire

Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
SA	A	N	DA	SDA
	2	3	4	5

Data were analysed accordingly and mean and percentage of the obtained data was gathered by descriptive analysis while using SPSS. Hence the result was gained by the research for the achievement of research objectives.

The mean of overall Perceptions showed that the change brought by FBISE could have a positive effect on the overall system. As the responses of English teachers are in favour of the change. The standard deviation and mean showed that most participants agreed with the change. Overall, the responses showed that the students are confused with the implementation of the new system of examination. They need to be better oriented with the concept of SLOs. All the stakeholders should be aware of the pros and cons; positive and negative perceptions of the new system and the confusion should be dissipated. So that the required results could be attained and real benefits of education could be seen in the society. Here is analysis of some of the teacher's responses:

Table 2: *I am familiar with the concept of Student Learning Outcomes (SLOs)*

	Strongly agree	Agree	Strongly Disagree	Total
Frequency	84	24	1	109
Percent	23.3	6.7	.3	30.3
Valid Percent	77.1	22.0	.9	100.0
Cumulative Percent	77.1	99.1	100.0	

CONCLUSIONS: The SLOs based examination has a strategic effect on the overall education system and its outcomes. All stakeholders want to get the maximum output from the educational activities. Student Learning Outcomes are the statements that describe what a learner could be able to know, understand, apply and create at the end of a certain learning process. These statements are often

exhibited in terms of an amalgamation of knowledge, skills, abilities, attitudes, and comprehension. From the current investigation it could be extracted that generally all the teachers and the students are concerned about the education and with the outcomes of the process. Teachers are especially worried about the overall standards of education as there is a perception that the education standards are rapidly deteriorating in Pakistan compared to the past standards. To dissipate this concept FBISE Islamabad launched a new system of examination that is commonly known as SLOs based examination system.

The launch of SLOs under the prevailing circumstances is both optimistic as well as sceptic. Therefore, the expressed feelings of confusion, apprehension, uncertainty, along with hopefulness and optimism. A majority of respondents indicated confidence in favour of the change brought by FBISE.

The majority opinionated agreeing with the change and this optimism can lead to affect the policies of other board working in the country. Although, teachers were divided whether to support the change or not, but majority nodded in favour of the change. They surely need proper orientation sessions which are rarely provided. Teachers didn't dismiss the change rather they showed interest in the process of change and SLOs. This can partly be calculated that some of the teachers might not be happy with the objective based learning as it is precisely targeted and challenging.

were

full

There could be another assumption that they don't want to stick with certain parameters and say that they just want to teach the content and get it reproduce, easy and very clear, rather than to improve the skills and ultimately if the concept taught isn't understood they can say that they are not responsible for any failure of students

in future as the exam content is different than what has been taught. The gap between the teachers and the examiner is also a real challenge. When we talk about SLOs there should be a good integration between the pedagogy and assessment board.

As SLOs based examination system approach is to prepare students for real life the content of assessment should be made more innovative and based on real life situations, so that the effect expected from change could be seen quite clearly and the perception that now the students

won't retain any data can be dissipated.

The management of educational institutes needs to understand the change and more exposure to the change should be provided to the teachers.

The integration of the whole system is very important. Information technology can play a vital role as benchmarks can be settled precisely.

This research was quantitative, questionnaires for students and teachers were used. The data were compiled and SPSS was used to analyse the obtained data

Findings: Students Learning Outcomes based examination system has been accepted by teachers as the results shows that overall rate is 1.2 / 5 with the standard deviation of .55 which clearly shows that acceptance level is extremely high.

1. The teachers are involved in the process of getting familiar with the change as it is 1.6/5 which is better than overall perception. It can be calculated logically that gradually the acceptance level could be higher. The response showed involvement level was really high and the future Perceptions of SLOs based examination are good and bright as per the data depiction.

2. The improvement in writing skills and getting better score results show that the change can positively affect the performance of the students and teachers.

Discussion

One of the objectives of the current study wanted "To identify the challenges of SLOs based examination for teachers of English Language at

HSSC level in students' writing skills?" The investigation showed that the teachers had following challenges:

- Familiarity with the SLOs, though the majority of respondents found it familiar
- Their expertise needs to be improved in development of SLOs
- Marking SLOs based examination was difficult
- To have opportunities for involvement in the process of development

The second objective was "To pinpoint the challenges faced by students regarding SLOs based examination at HSSC level in their writing skills" The challenges for students were:

- The students are not fully familiar with the SLOs
- The rote learning concept and SLOs based testing kept them confused
- Delimited content that is taught versus the unseen content kept them baffled.

The third objective was "To find out the Perceptions of SLOs based examination of English language at HSSC Level." The Perceptions of SLOs based examination are:

- Bright not grim
- Better grades possible
- Better comprehension of concept
- Improved the writing skills of the English language
- More acceptability

This study clearly shows the Perceptions are positive and as the change gradually settles down and the result could become more attractive and effective to achieve the targets of education

The panic among all stakeholders is a real phenomenon and the results of this study show that all concerned are a little confused about the changes made in the testing system by the FBISE but on the other hand the results also show that the writing skills have improved and the marks obtained by students have also increased which indicate that the Perceptions of SLOs based examination are good.

The literature review shows that in other countries like South Africa and Australia the situation was almost similar to this. In South Africa when "Outcome based Education" was launched there was a negative attitude of teachers as it was found out *"The investigation revealed that more than half*

of South African teachers hold negative perceptions and attitudes towards OBE.” Giessen-Hood, C. (1999). Whereas here the situation is good and the acceptance level is higher.

The challenges identified by researchers about SLOs based examination are lack of training and time management (Channa, et al. 2023) and the current study also identified that the orientation sessions need to be arranged to train the teachers as well as students to achieve the optimal level of effectiveness.

“They found that using SLO-based grading changed the way instructors look at their student's work” (Bengiamin, et al. 2012). The population of teachers participating in the current study also had the same opinion as the majority of respondents agreed with the statement that teachers face difficulties while marking SLOs based assessments.

The change should be brought gradually and the content which is used for testing should be from the seen content. As the majority of students refuse to accept totally unseen content.

The teachers also need to be well aware of the need and they must be trained by workshops and orientation sessions. The perception is very important for the prospect of acceptability of a change. As there is a trend among students to compare different boards for their results.

The major difference can be found between the “Mean of students’ responses, their understanding and Teachers’ understanding”. The learners’ understanding is far lower than the teachers’. All stakeholders must understand the SLOs based examination system and they should accept its utility for better outputs.

Conclusions

- i. The SLOs based examination system should be gradually implemented. The change that is expected to bring a positive change which is implemented to reduce cramming and making the whole system outcomes bases can be more effective if the ratio of knowledge and understanding based questions could be kept and gradually reduced to minimum level. The change that is abrupt could not produce the result unless proper planning and implementation is not used. The damage can be reduced and the stakeholders can be satisfied and can be a part of change to make it effective.

- ii. There should be more orientation sessions for teachers, students and parents to achieve better results. The awareness campaigns should be increased and to achieve the desired results educating the stakeholder could play a vital role. Though the majority of respondents said that they know SLOs but the doubtfulness was quite clear when they replied about their satisfaction level. .
- iii. Majority of teachers and students are in favour of the SLOs based examination system. As it is very difficult to leave the comfort zone, so some of the stakeholders participating in the current research also expressed clearly that they are not in favour of the SLOs based examination system. The authorities need to arrange sessions with the stakeholders and the step-by-step process needs to be shown to the stakeholders to get the results.
- iv. Majority of teachers and students believe that SLOs based systems could have a negative impact on overall performance. As the system is implemented for the high-stake examination which resultantly affects all the stakeholder. The system needs to be made applicable from grass root level to the highest level.
- v. More than half of the teachers say that SLOs based examination system has impacted positively on the creative writing of their students. The educationists who responded in the current studies surely agreed that the creative writing skills are improved after the implementation of the SLOs based examination system which is a ray of hope that gradually the system could affect all positively. Deep learning and critical thinking could be widespread among the learners.
- vi. The students say that it is easier to get better grades in SLOs based examinations. One more positive aspect is that the participants expressed that the new system isn't a threat and can help the learners to achieve their desired results and grading shows that the Perceptions of SLOs based examination are bright and it is going to be the talk of the town soon.

Recommendations

- i. More teachers training sessions should be held and they should be prepared to make their formative tests as per the pattern of SLOs.

ii. Parents should also be involved in the orientation sessions about SLOs.

Future Researches

- i. To investigate whether SLOs based examination systems play a purposeful role in the quality of education further researches can open new avenues.
- ii. This study was conducted at HSSC level with English language teachers in Pakistan. Furthermore, conducting similar study in different other subjects would be worth presenting.
- iii. This research was conducted in Punjab; further research can be conducted in a different demographic area.
- iv. This research was based on quantitative research; it could be conducted while taking interviews from the experts of education with decades of experience and hands on knowledge of assessment.
- v. A comparative study can also be done with two groups of learners, one in Objective based learning process and other in outcome-based learning process and their outputs can be compared.
- vi. SLOs based formative testing can also be analysed for making micro level changes in the testing process.
- vii. Pre-school testing can also be conducted based on SLOs and certain instruments can be made for checking the skills of learners.
- viii. Students' academic performance and course content relation can also be analysed while keeping SLOs record.
- ix. Changing contents and raising bench marks can also be analysed for determining the most suitable content for better SLOs.

References

- Abdulrahman, M. D., Faruk, N., Oloyede, A. A., Surajudeen-Bakinde, N. T., Olawoyin, L. A., Mejabi, O. V., & Azeez, A. L. (2020). Multimedia tools in the teaching and learning processes: A systematic review. *Heliyon*, 6(11).
- Adams, N. E. (2015). Bloom's taxonomy of cognitive learning objectives. *Journal of the Medical Library Association: JMLA*, 103(3), 152.
- Ahmed, A., & Ahmed, N. (2017). Comparative Analysis of Rote Learning on High and Low Achievers in Graduate and Undergraduate Programs. *Journal of Education and Educational Development*, 4(1), 111-129.

Journal for Current Sign

Online ISSN (3006-1504)

Print ISSN (3006-1490)

- Allesch, A., & Brunner, P. H. (2014). Assessment methods for solid waste management: A literature review. *Waste Management & Research*, 32(6), 461-473.
- Celano, M., Hazzard, A., Webb, C., & McCall, C. (1996). Treatment of traumagenic beliefs among sexually abused girls and their mothers: An evaluation study. *Journal of abnormal child psychology*, 24, 1-17.
- Ghaicha, A. (2016). Theoretical Framework for Educational Assessment: A Synoptic Review. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 7(24), 212-231.
- Iqbal, K., Hayat, S., & Suleman, Q. (2019). Evaluation of students learning outcomes based assessment and teachers' role at primary level. *Journal of Research in Social Sciences*, 7(1), 186-200.
- Moss, C. M., & Brookhart, S. M. (2019). Advancing formative assessment in every classroom: *A guide for instructional leaders*. ASCD.